

Original Research Article

Development of Teaching Materials to Write Negotiation Text Based on Literacy

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to know: (1) the process of preparing the development of teaching Materials to write negotiation text based literacy, (2) the feasibility of teaching Materials that are tested by Material validation and design on writing negotiation text based literacy, (3) the effectiveness of to write negotiation text based literacy in the class X private high school students of Saint Lucia. This type of research is research and development based on Borg and Gall development model. Trial subjects consist of Material experts, design experts, Indonesian teachers, Private High School students of Saint Lucia. Data on the quality of this product were collected through a questionnaire and a negotiated text writing test. The results of this study show that: (1) validation of Material otherwise eligible with excellent average. Obtained feasibility of the contents of 86.71% in very good category, the acquisition feasibility of 91.34% in very good category and the acquisition of language feasibility 87,50% in very good category, (2) validation by design expert with average 81, 67% in very good category, (3) individual trials expressed very well with an average total percentage of 88.83%, (4) The acquisition of small group trial results is very good with an average percentage of 88.51 %, (5) The acquisition of limited field trial results was excellent with average percentage score of 90.8%; (6) the effectiveness of teaching Materials showed a postage percentage of 80.09% higher than the pretest presentation of 70.80 %. Thus, the module of writing negotiation text that has been developed is feasible and effective for use as a learning resource.

Keywords: development, negotiation text, literacy

INTRODUCTION

One of the fundamental changes in the curriculum of 2013, especially in the field of Indonesian language learning occurs in the paradigm of linguistic unit determination that becomes the basis of learning Materials. Changes to the Material have an impact on changing learning methods. The language unit that became the basis of learning is text. Thus, language learning takes into consideration the context of the language usage situation itself. Citing or composing text for a particular purpose

means choosing the form and structure of the text that will be used for the message to be delivered correctly. The choice of form or structure of text by speakers to achieve a goal in a communicative social activity is determined by the context of the situation faced.

The context of the situation is the unity of some inseparable and interdependent elements of what is being said, who is involved in the conversation (the nature and role of each, and the nature of the relationship between one another),

channel used (written, spoken, combination of both), as well as its social purpose (persuasive, deductive, expository).

A communication action taken to achieve a certain goal is manifested in concrete form of text for one common purpose, usually not used one text that is exactly the same but varied in terms of content and form of language used. Although similar, the similarities between the texts can be easily identified, even with people who have no about linguistics or communication studies. Some texts that have similarities in action are done that are usually grouped in one same genre.

The results of observations of researchers with teachers of Indonesian language subjects in Private High School Saint Lucia, explained that learning to understand and write the text of negotiation still not maximized. Constraints of teachers such as students are less able to write or produce text negotiations, consequently the value obtained by students under the Minimum Criterion (KKM). This is supported by ^[1] with the title Influence Learning Model Inventions on Writing Negotiation Text, says that most of the students' difficulties in learning the Indonesian language is part producing text. When students have understood the texts that have been studied, but after being assigned to produce the text the students find it difficult and confused to do it. It is also found in producing negotiated texts because the text of the negotiating lesson is a lesson they know less

Examples presented are certainly inadequate for the needs of learners that have difficulty in studying negotiation text Material, consequently the average value of daily repeat on negotiation text Material is 70 with 60% completeness, this is supported by. ^[2] The ability of students in writing the text of negotiation should be improved because with the ability of students to write text negotiation students are invited to be more wise in social interaction. But in fact students are less interested in writing negotiation writing because inadequate

learning and teaching Materials lead to a lack of motivating students to think more critically and actively, resulting in less knowledge in writing negotiating texts, this is also supported by. ^[3] The low learning outcomes of these learners make the researcher interested to develop teaching Materials to write negotiation text based literacy. Teaching Materials are all forms of Materials used to assist teachers in implementing the learning process. This is supported by research from. ^[4]

^[5] explains that the selection of learning Materials should be based on objectives. That is, the Material is only considered taken if it has relevance to the competence being learned. Selection of Materials that are not in accordance with the competencies in question will only result in not achieving the desired goals. The teaching Materials are also determined by model selection as it becomes the determinant of the learning process in the classroom. Several previous studies on writing the text of negotiation, obtained data that learners learn the results in writing the text of negotiation is still low. The results are in the research conducted by. ^[6,7]

The importance of the development of Materials based literacy certainly provides a positive impact for learners. The National Institute for Literacy defines literacy as the individual's ability to read, speak, count and solve problems at the level of expertise required in work, family, and society. In general, literacy activities are identical with reading and writing activities. The Prague Declaration in 2003 mentions that literacy also includes how one communicates within a society.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Studying Materials

^[8] said that Material refer to anything which is done by writer, teacher or learners to provide source of language input and to exploit those source in ways which maximize the like hood intake: in other word the supplying of information about and experience of language in ways design

to promote language learning. [9] define that the Material as a way of influencing the quality of the classroom interaction and the language use, Material can be in the form of a textbook, a workbook, a cassette, a CD-ROM, a video, and a photocopied handout and [10] said that Materials is one that is rich in unanswered questions. Building a mental library of relevant “bits” of information and cultivating it by allowing reflection-time to try out various arrangements of the bits, allows them to finally fall into a pattern that gives new insight or suggests a new solution.

Negotiation Text

[11] States that negotiation is an area full of rigorous knowledge and effort to achieve the basic principle "you are fortunate, I also do not lose", negotiation must be a balance point (equilibrium), where both parties trust and agree. Negotiation is a process of communication between two or more people to develop the best solution that is most beneficial to the parties involved. This is supported by the opinion of [12] who said that the negotiation is the process of recognizing, organizing, and agree on the terms of a transaction and the structure of negotiation includes orientation, demand, fulfillment, supply, approval, purchase and closing.

Literacy

Literacy is the ability to communicate meaning through reading and writing. [13] Literacy is the use of socially-, and historically-, and culturally-situated practices of creating and interpreting meaning through texts. It entails at least a tacit awareness of the relationships between textual conventions and their context of use and, ideally, the ability to reflect critically on those relationships. Because it is purpose-sensitive, literacy is dynamic - not static - and variable across and within discourse communities and cultures. It draws on a wide range of cognitive abilities, on knowledge of written and spoken language, on knowledge of genres, and on cultural knowledge. Carolline on her book “Literacy Learning” literacy is how young

children learn to read and write. [14] Literacy as the ability to read and write.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The study was conducted at SMA Santa Lucia in Batang Kuis KM 14, Medan. The research will be conducted from February to March 2018. The population of this research and development is a class X private high school student of Saint Lucia. To see the effectiveness of the developed product, the researcher only takes samples using random sampling technique, researchers take the sample of the study amounted to 34 students. This research uses Research and Development (R & D) method.

The data collection instrument in this development is a valuation instrument to assess the products that have been developed. The principal instruments used to collect data in this development are the validation sheet and outcome learning test (essay). The validation sheet is used to get the valuation data from the validator about the developed product, the Indonesian language textbook on the negotiation text Material for grade X SMA.

Table 1. Grid Instrument Questionnaire Feasibility Design by Design Expert.

Component Assessment Indicator	Number of Questions
The physical size of teaching Materials	2
Cover	9
Design of teaching Materials	19

The data obtained is data about the state of the Indonesian textbook on the negotiated text Material that has been developed. This data is collected through expert validation, questionnaire distributed to students. Research instruments for validators and individual tests, small groups or limited field groups are created in the form of a Likert scale that has been scored as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Criteria Answers Validated Item Instruments with the Likert Scale with the Scores

Answer	Score
Excellent	4
Good	3
Not Good	2
Bad	1

Then analyzed descriptively quantitatively by calculating the percentage of indicators for each category on developed teaching Materials.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Product development of teaching Materials in the form of module to write negotiation text based literacy developed by considering the aspects of learning Materials and instructional design. Product development research that has been done is directed to produce a product in the form of teaching Materials in the form of modules on learning to write negotiation text for students of class X Private High School of Saint Lucia used to improve the learning process and competence of learners. Therefore, in the process this research is carried out by beginning of preliminary study. Then designing teaching Materials, product validation, revision and refinement based on validation data analysis from Material experts, Materials design experts, followed by individual testing, small group trials, and Trial Field Trial to produce appropriate teaching Materials in accordance with the characteristics of the field of study and students as users.

Aspects are revised and refined based on data analysis and testing as well as input from Material experts, Materials design experts, teachers and learners as users of this resource. The findings of the teaching Materials product in the form of a module entitled "Writing Negotiation Text Based Literacy" which has been tested can be detailed as follows:

1. Theoretically, literacy-based learning is best used in negotiating text writing activities because students can more easily put ideas down when discovering the literacy directly. Literacy can be obtained through 4 stages: 1) accessing information, 2) analyzing information, 3) evaluating information and 4) producing information. The process of writing negotiation text based on literacy-based learning method that includes 4 stages: 1) tracing the source of ideas obtained from the activities of

accessing information. Information accessing activities can be obtained based on active observation of what is to be studied. Observation can be done by visiting directly to the desired place, reading a book, encyclopedia or searching on the internet source. 2) analyze the information, at this stage the students analyze the results that are accessed. This means that students attempt to investigate, parse, differentiate, sorting to develop a text of negotiation either in the form of dialogue or narration, concepts or laws and procedures on something that becomes the object of attention. 3) Evaluate, this stage is a process to provide information about how far something has been achieved and known, how the difference in achievement with a certain standard and how the benefits derived from information that has been accessed and analyzed. 4) produce, at this stage students have been able to compile negotiation text.

2. Obtaining the result of requirement analysis to teacher and student that all teachers (100%) stated need of instructional Material developed in accordance with curriculum of 2013 in learning process and most of learner (90,62%) stated need of learning Materials developed based on literacy in learning process.

3. Assessments made by the Material experts include 3 aspects of the assessment, namely the feasibility of the content, feasibility of presentation and language assessment. The results of the assessment of the Material content feasibility aspect are stated "excellent" with an average percentage of 88.23%. The feasibility assessment of presentation is "excellent" with an average percentage of 92.36%, and the language assessment aspect is "excellent" with an average percentage of 86.80%.

4. The results of validation of teaching Materials by learning media experts expressed "excellent" with an average total percentage of 82.35%. The total percentage gain on the cover Material size was 87.5% in the "excellent" category, the design of the

Material cover was 81.94% in the "good" category and the content design of the teaching Materials was 77.63% in the good category.

5. The results of responses by Indonesian teachers to teaching Materials in the form of a module of negotiation text module are "excellent" with an average percentage of 95%.

6. The results of the trial assessment of the students were conducted in 3 processes: individual testing (3 students), small group trial (9 students) and Limited Field Trial (32 students). The acquisition of individual test results is "good" with an average percentage of 88.83%. The acquisition of small group trial results was "excellent" with an average percentage of 88.51%. The acquisition of a Limited Field Trial result is stated "excellent" with a total percentage of average score of 90.8%.

7. The average acquisition of students in the writing negotiation text test based literacy before using the developed Material of 77.66 while the average gain after using the Material 90.15. This proves that the result of student learning in literacy-based negotiation writing test increases with the difference of value obtained from pretest to posttest that is 12,49. Furthermore, teaching Materials in the form of literacy-based modules are effectively used in learning to write negotiation texts.

The findings of the research results described above, it can be concluded that the results of development of teaching Materials to writing negotiation text based literacy for the feasibility of teaching Materials are declared eligible in the category of "excellent" and for student learning outcomes expressed able to improve student learning outcomes in writing text literacy-based negotiation.

Derived from the use of teaching Materials is the concept presented easy to learn, understand and systematically. Teaching Materials provide students with the opportunity to learn at their own pace independently, learn to be more focused and less boring as it comes with Materials,

examples of analysis and practice questions. The repetition should be done when viewing the scores obtained to make learners better understand the Material.

CONCLUSION

Based on the formulation of the problem, the purpose of research, research results and discussion in research development of teaching Material based literacy on the negotiation text can be concluded that (1) The result of analysis shows that 62.24% of students have not understood negotiation text Material, 71.35% of students stated that they only use government education Materials without any other handbook and 87.90% of students need other teaching Materials, especially Materials teach the literacy; (2) The product of teaching Materials to write negotiation text was developed for High School students of Private Senior High School Saint Lucia is eligible and worthy of use. This is evidenced by the validation results of Material experts covering the feasibility of the content with an average of 88.23% on very good criteria, the feasibility of presentation with an average of 92.36% on very good criteria, language aspect with an average of 86.80% on excellent criteria and design expert validation with an average of 82.35% on very good criteria; (3) The use of teaching Materials to write negotiation text based literacy is more effective than textbooks that use of students. This is evidenced by the results of better student learning that is the use of textbooks (pretest) 77.66% with enough category and the use of teaching Materials based literacy (post-test) 90.15% with excellent category.

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How to cite this article: Hutahaeen F, Adisaputera A, Solin M. Development of teaching materials to write negotiation text based on literacy. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2018; 5(5):22-27.
